

Exploring the implications of discrete categories along an acoustic correlate

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Abstract

The present paper provides empirical evidence that the change in intensity during the production of the Spanish alveolar tap in a variety of Mexican Spanish is best characterized by two distributions instead of one, replicating a recent finding from another variety of Spanish. The finding of multiple ‘categories’ along an acoustic gradient is discussed in the context of the implications for phonetic theory and analyzing acoustic measurements. We outline future steps and questions that we believe will be important to address, starting with the nature of statistical vs. phonetic categories, as well as incorporating knowledge of acoustics-to-articulatory mapping into the discussion of phonetic variability.

Introduction

Speech production research that has investigated several varieties of Spanish has demonstrated that there is substantial acoustic variation in the production of the alveolar tap (Amengual, 2016; Bradley & Willis, 2012; Henriksen, 2015; Kim & Repiso-Puigdeliura, 2020; Willis & Bradley, 2008). Two example tokens outlining this variability are depicted in Figure 1. Recent modelling of the intensity difference (IntDiff) between the minimum during the tap and the maximum of the surrounding vowels by Perry et al.

(2024) showed that an assumption of two latent pronunciation variants of the tap, coded into the model as two distinct distributions, was required in order to adequately model the data. The first goal of the present study is to analyze a corpus comprised of spontaneous speech from a variety of Mexican Spanish to investigate whether this finding replicates in a new set of data from another dialect. Our second goal is to explore what having discrete categories along acoustic correlates could mean for phonetic theory, especially when this variation is generally thought of as gradient.

Figure 1. Spectrograms and waveforms of taps with intensity curves overlaid. The top panel shows a tap produced as a stop, while the bottom panel shows a highly reduced variant produced as an approximant.

It is generally accepted that the phonetic variation we observe in speech production can be thought of as falling along a continuum from carefully enunciated speech on one end to highly ‘reduced’ speech on the other (Tucker & Mukai, 2023). There have been several proposals which attempt to explain this variation not as noise, but instead as part of the signal that can help us understand the cognitive mechanisms of speech production (e.g., Aylett & Turk, 2004; Bell et al., 2009; Jaeger, 2010). One such proposal is H&H Theory, put forth by Lindblom (1990), which states that phonetic variation results partially from obedience to the principle of economy of effort while producing speech, leading to more phonetic reduction in situations where the signal will be easier to discriminate.

If we assume that the phonetic variability present in speech can inform cognitive models of speech production, then the physical properties of the acoustic signal need to be properly accounted for when modelling this variation. That is to say that models with acoustic correlates as the dependent variable need to, at minimum, be compatible with the patterns we observe when measuring speech. We also need to consider the fact that any cognitive pressures shaping speech production are doing so through changes in articulation, which are then responsible for the acoustic signal. Most studies which analyze acoustic correlates of reduction implicitly or explicitly treat this variation as gradient within phonemic categories, and generally do not provide evidence that the statistical models are descriptively adequate. In contrast with gradient within-category phonetic variability, some analyses do show both gradient and categorical variation. Examples of this include the voicing implementation of obstruents in English (Davidson, 2016), schwa deletion in French (Bürki et al., 2011), and, central

to the present paper, alveolar tap variation in Spanish (Perry et al., 2024).

The first goal of the present study is to attempt to replicate a finding from Perry and colleagues (hereafter P24), namely, that analyzing the IntDiff of Spanish alveolar taps using a finite mixture model with two distributions leads to a better fit to the data than using a single distribution. To identify whether the bimodal nature of IntDiff reported in P24 can be sidestepped by employing a different proxy of consonant reduction, we also look at another acoustic measurement: the maximum velocity of the intensity curve leaving the tap.

Materials and methods

The data analyzed in the present paper is spontaneous speech data from first-language speakers of Spanish from Querétaro, México (N=13). Their speech was recorded using a head-mounted microphone in a sound-attenuated booth during a phone conversation with a friend or relative, which lasted approximately 15 minutes. The speech of the participants was orthographically transcribed and subsequently aligned using the Montreal Forced Aligner (McAuliffe et al., 2017). For additional details regarding the creation and preparation of the corpus, the reader is directed to Hernandez et al. (2023).

To model the acoustic variability of alveolar taps in our corpus, we extracted acoustic measurements and information about the tap and surrounding words and segments with a script in Praat (Boersma & Weenink, 2022) as in P24. This gave us our intensity measures as well as the quality of the surrounding vowels, the identity of the word containing the tap, as well as the average speech rate of the utterance in syllables per second. We also measured the maximum slope of the intensity curve leaving the tap, which has been used as a measure of lenition in previous studies of other consonants (e.g., Simonet et al., 2012).

Statistical analysis

To model the variation in IntDiff, we fit a series of generalized Bayesian hierarchical models using package *brms* (Bürkner, 2017) in *R* (R Core Team, 2021). All models predicted IntDiff using an additive combination of the following variables: log unigram frequency as calculated from the OpenSubtitles corpus (Lison & Tiedemann, 2016), log local speech rate (syllables/s), whether the preceding and following vowels bore lexical stress, and the vowel quality of the preceding and following vowels. All models had a varying intercept for speaker.

The first model had a single skew-normal distribution as the likelihood function. Following P24, we then moved to fitting finite mixture models comprised of two skew-normal distributions. In order to aid model identification, this model was fit using informative priors for the intercepts for the means of the two distributions, which were based on the posteriors of the models fit in P24, but with wider scale parameters. All population-level effects were centred at zero to provide regularization, with the priors' scale parameters informed by the largest relevant effects reported in P24. Finally, we fit a model with three skew-normal distributions, again with the intercepts being informed by P24, this time in the form of the descriptive statistics reported for the qualitative categories coded visually using a spectrogram. As one would expect due to the increased complexity, this last model had computational issues.

Results

The first goal of the present paper was to replicate the finding of P24. Specifically, we wanted to know if the predictive performance of our statistical model was improved when we modelled IntDiff of Spanish taps using more than one distribution. This corresponds to the

assumption that there are two latent categories of the tap, which were referred to as 'reduced' and 'unreduced' by P24.

This finding is replicated with our present data. In Table 1, we report the model comparisons using the leave-one-out information criterion (LOOIC; Vehtari et al., 2017), which show that the model with two skew-normal distributions outperforms the model with a single distribution, and that the estimated improvement is more than four times the standard error of the difference. This improvement from one skew-normal distribution to two was a less certain improvement compared to the one reported in P24, where the improvement in LOOIC was more than 8 times the standard error of the difference.

Table 1. The results of the model comparison via LOOIC. The second column shows the difference in the expected log predictive density (ELPD) compared to the best model. The third column shows the standard error (SE) of the difference; a measure of uncertainty regarding the comparison. The models with likelihoods comprised of two and three skew-normal distributions have similar estimated out-of-sample predictive accuracy, and they both outperform the model with only a single distribution.

Model	Difference in ELPD	SE of difference
2-dist	0	0
3-dist	-1.8	7.1
1-dist	-41.8	9.8

In Figure 2 below, we include a visualization of the maximum velocity of the intensity slope coming out of the tap, as well as a visualization of IntDiff. The distribution for the maximum velocity of the intensity slope is clearly bimodal, indicating that the issue of a single distribution being inadequate for modelling the data is not an issue with IntDiff specifically, and it at least

extends to one other acoustic correlate used to measure stop reduction.

Another difference between the present findings and those from P24 are the visual nature of the posterior predictive checks. While the skew-normal likelihood was clearly inappropriate for modelling IntDiff in P24, this may not have been as clear for the current data. Posterior checks presented in Figure 3 show only a small visual improvement when shifting from generalized linear models to finite mixture models.

Figure 2. The estimated density distribution of the maximum velocity of the intensity slope leading out of the tap for the present data (A) and the estimated density distributions of IntDiff for the present dataset and the hand-corrected data from P24 (B).

Discussion

The finding of two latent pronunciation variants improving our modelling of the IntDiff of Spanish taps, which has now been found for two different varieties of the language (Mexican and Iberian), raises questions regarding acoustic measurement as well as what this finding means for phonetic theories. In the present discussion, we do not offer any definitive explanation or account of this, but instead sketch out what we believe to be important considerations that deserve to be empirically evaluated

moving forward. However, before we turn to this more general discussion, we discuss the differences between the findings presented here and those from P24.

The first notable difference is the distribution of IntDiff itself. P24 presented a clear bimodal distribution of IntDiff (Figure 2B). In contrast, the deviation of the present distribution from a skew-normal distribution was not as obvious and may not have raised concern for all speech researchers (Figure 3A). Potential reasons for this difference are numerous. Cross-dialectal differences cannot be ruled out, but conclusions regarding potential differences are hampered by differences in the recording equipment and elicitation method, which could feasibly be responsible for some of the observed differences. The data analyzed in the present paper are from phone conversations between two people, while those analyzed by P24 took place in a face-to-face setting in groups of three. Any future work looking to make comparisons across dialects would be strengthened by keeping recording and elicitation methods consistent.

We turn now to how we might integrate these findings concerning the production of the Spanish tap into the body of research investigating the cognitive factors at play during speech production. The first avenue that we believe should be investigated is bringing articulatory data to bear on this issue. As acknowledged in P24, it is possible that the latent categories we observe in our acoustic correlates are, in fact, not present in articulation. It is also possible that the nature of the acoustics is related to the movement and/or timing of multiple articulators.

Figure 3. Depicted in this figure are the posterior predictive checks comparing the observed IntDiff values in black to ten datasets simulated from the model. Panel A corresponds to the model with a likelihood comprised of a single skew-normal distribution, panel B to the model with two distributions, and panel C to the model with three distributions.

Research that has attempted to map articulation to acoustics and vice-versa has shown the relationship is complex, and often employs mixture models or other models with multiple discrete states to handle the mapping (Ananthakrishnan & Engwall, 2011). It is possible that these flexible models are needed because the complex coordination and movement of the vocal tract creates statistical grouping effects in acoustic correlates that simple regression cannot account for.

If, after examining the articulation, it is still clear that there are multiple discrete pronunciation variants of the Spanish tap, we can explore the ramifications for theories of speech production and sound systems in general. As these variants would not be phonemic in nature, we would most readily refer to them as allophones in free variation. However, as discussed by Pierrehumbert (2002), it is desirable for several reasons to keep the total number of allophones to a minimum when outlining a probabilistic model of phonology that integrates lexical effects. This issue of multiple variants may extend to stop consonants more generally, as they are often reduced in both spontaneous and read speech (e.g., Barry & Andreeva, 2001; Warner & Tucker, 2011). It will have to be determined whether reduced variants

have their own representation in the speech production system, or if general patterns of articulatory undershoot and/or coarticulation can be solely responsible for patterns of reduction that are both gradient and categorical.

Overall, the findings of the present study and those of P24 have raised several questions regarding patterns of variability in the production of the Spanish tap and how to account for them in a cognitive model of speech production. Even if these more complex mixture models are only relevant in accounting for the complex mapping between articulation and acoustics, they need to be integrated into phonetic analyses so that we can better capture the wide range of acoustic variability present in the speech signal when using statistical models to understand potential cognitive effects on speech production.

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